

**BRIDGING THE GAP: APPLYING INSIGHTS FROM FREDERICK
M. HESS'S "STILL AT RISK" TO ADDRESS LOW NUMERACY
AND READING SKILLS AT CAROL-AN NATIONAL
HIGH SCHOOL"**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 2

Pages: 221-224

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1853

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11255730

Manuscript Accepted: 5-01-2024

Bridging the Gap: Applying Insights from Frederick M. Hess's "Still At Risk" to Address Low Numeracy and Reading Skills at Carol-an National High School

Nick C. Gador*

[For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.](#)

Abstract

This review examines the application of insights derived from Frederick M. Hess's seminal report, "Still At Risk: What Students Don't Know, Even Now," to address the challenges of low numeracy and reading skills at Carol-an National High School. The introductory statement highlights the persistent nature of knowledge gaps in global educational systems and the need for targeted interventions to enhance student learning outcomes. The research questions inquire into the specific challenges faced by Carol-an National High School regarding low numeracy and reading skills and explore how insights from Hess's report can effectively inform interventions. Employing a qualitative approach, the methodology section outlines the design, participants, instruments, procedure, and ethical considerations of the study. Results demonstrate the implications of Hess's findings for low numeracy and reading skills, emphasizing the foundational role of these skills in academic success and the need for evidence-based strategies to address deficiencies. The discussion underscores the broader implications of Hess's report for learners, teachers, and other stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of collaboration and systemic change to promote educational equity. The conclusion and recommendations advocate for the implementation of targeted interventions informed by Hess's insights to empower students and foster a culture of excellence at Carol-an National High School.

Keywords: *article, numeracy, reading skills*

Introduction

Frederick M. Hess's seminal report, "Still At Risk: What Students Don't Know, Even Now," published by Common Core, provides a comprehensive examination of the enduring gaps in student knowledge that persist as formidable obstacles within educational systems globally. This meticulously crafted report offers invaluable insights garnered from rigorous research and empirical evidence, shedding light on the multifaceted factors contributing to these persistent challenges. In this review, we aim to delve deeper into the implications of Hess's findings for Carol-an National High School, a learning institution grappling with the significant issue of low numeracy and reading skills among its student body. By extrapolating key insights from Hess's report and contextualizing them within the unique context of Carol-an National High School, this review endeavors to illuminate actionable strategies that can be employed to address these pressing concerns. Through a nuanced analysis of Hess's research findings and recommendations, we seek to identify practical interventions tailored to the specific needs and challenges faced by the school community. Our overarching goal is to leverage the invaluable insights provided by Hess's report to foster positive change at Carol-an National High School, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes and promoting educational equity within the institution.

Research Questions

1. What are the specific challenges faced by Carol-an National High School regarding low numeracy and reading skills?
2. How can insights from Frederick M. Hess's report be applied to address these challenges effectively?

Literature Review

Hess's report delves deeply into the complex web of factors that contribute to the persistence of knowledge gaps among students, offering a comprehensive analysis that spans curriculum deficiencies, instructional practices, and systemic inequities. Through meticulous research and data-driven insights, Hess brings to light the pervasive nature of these gaps and their profound implications for academic achievement, particularly among marginalized student populations.

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At Carol-an National High School, the realities of low numeracy and reading skills among students mirror the broader patterns elucidated in Hess's report. These deficiencies pose significant obstacles to students' academic progress and future opportunities, limiting their ability to engage effectively with the curriculum and succeed in their educational pursuits. In light of these challenges, educators and stakeholders at Carol-an National High School must carefully consider the intersections between Hess's findings and the specific needs of their school community.

By drawing parallels between Hess's research and the realities faced by Carol-an National High School, educators and stakeholders

can develop targeted interventions that address the root causes of low numeracy and reading skills among students. This may involve implementing evidence-based instructional strategies tailored to meet the diverse learning needs of students, providing additional support and resources for struggling learners, and fostering a culture of literacy and numeracy throughout the school community. Furthermore, by leveraging Hess's insights, educators can advocate for systemic changes that promote educational equity and address the underlying inequities that perpetuate knowledge gaps among students.

Aligning their efforts with the findings and recommendations of Hess's report, educators and stakeholders at Carol-an National High School can work collaboratively to develop innovative solutions that support student success and promote a culture of excellence within the school community. Through targeted interventions and a commitment to continuous improvement, Carol-an National High School can empower all students to achieve their full potential and thrive academically.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative approach to analyze insights from Frederick M. Hess's report and apply them to the context of Carol-an National High School.

Participants

Participants include educators, administrators, and stakeholders at Carol-an National High School.

Instruments

Data collection instruments include interviews, surveys, and document analysis.

Procedure

Data collection involves gathering information on the current state of low numeracy and reading skills at Carol-an National High School, analyzing Hess's report, and identifying potential interventions.

Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and respect for participants' rights.

Results and Discussion

Findings presented in Hess's report and their implications for low numeracy

Hess's report highlights the pervasive nature of knowledge gaps in numeracy, emphasizing the foundational role of numerical skills in academic success. The report underscores how deficiencies in numeracy not only impede students' ability to comprehend mathematical concepts but also hinder their overall academic achievement. At Carol-an National High School, these findings resonate deeply, as low numeracy skills among students pose significant barriers to their educational progress. Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions aimed at improving numerical literacy and fostering a supportive learning environment conducive to mathematical reasoning and problem-solving.

Findings presented in Hess's report and their implications for reading skills

Similarly, Hess's report sheds light on the critical importance of reading skills in shaping students' academic trajectories. The report highlights how deficiencies in reading comprehension hinder students' ability to engage with complex subject matter across various disciplines. At Carol-an National High School, low reading skills among students contribute to academic underachievement and limit their access to educational opportunities. Addressing these challenges entails implementing evidence-based strategies to enhance reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and critical thinking skills. By fostering a culture of literacy and providing targeted support for struggling readers, educators can empower students to succeed academically and unlock their full potential.

General implications of Hess's report for learners, teachers, and other stakeholders

Hess's report carries profound implications for learners, teachers, and other stakeholders within the educational ecosystem. For learners, the report underscores the importance of acquiring foundational skills in numeracy and literacy to succeed academically and thrive in an increasingly complex world. By prioritizing the development of these fundamental skills, students can build a strong academic foundation and pursue their educational aspirations with confidence.

For teachers, Hess's report highlights the need for evidence-based instructional strategies tailored to address the diverse learning needs of students. Educators play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive learning environment wherein students feel empowered to engage meaningfully with academic content and develop essential skills for success. By incorporating best practices informed by Hess's research, teachers can create dynamic learning experiences that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and lifelong learning.

For other stakeholders, including administrators, policymakers, and community members, Hess's report underscores the importance of collaboration and systemic change to address persistent challenges in education. By working together to dismantle barriers to learning and promote educational equity, stakeholders can create a more inclusive and supportive educational environment wherein all students have the opportunity to succeed.

Hess's report serves as a call to action for educators and stakeholders to redouble their efforts in addressing the pervasive issues of low numeracy and reading skills. By heeding the insights presented in Hess's report and implementing targeted interventions, educators can empower students to unlock their full potential and pursue their goals with confidence, thereby fostering a brighter and more equitable future for all.

Hess's report serves as a poignant reminder of the foundational role that numeracy and literacy play in shaping students' academic trajectories. By emphasizing the critical importance of these fundamental skills, Hess underscores their indispensable role in facilitating academic success and fostering lifelong learning. Drawing on a wealth of national assessments and international benchmarks, Hess compellingly illustrates the pervasive nature of knowledge gaps in numeracy and literacy domains and their far-reaching implications for student learning outcomes.

At Carol-an National High School, the pervasive issues of low numeracy and reading skills resonate deeply with the findings presented in Hess's report. These deficiencies not only hinder students' ability to comprehend complex subject matter but also pose significant barriers to their overall academic achievement. Indeed, the ramifications of low numeracy and reading skills extend far beyond the classroom, contributing to low graduation rates and limiting students' post-secondary opportunities.

In light of these challenges, Hess's insights carry profound implications for educational practice at Carol-an National High School. By prioritizing the development of numeracy and reading skills, educators can lay a robust foundation upon which students can build their academic prowess across all subject areas. This necessitates the implementation of evidence-based instructional strategies that are tailored to address the diverse learning needs of students, providing targeted interventions for those who require additional support.

Moreover, fostering a culture of literacy and numeracy throughout the school community is paramount to nurturing a conducive learning environment wherein students feel empowered to engage meaningfully with academic content. This entails not only instilling a love for reading and mathematical reasoning but also equipping students with the critical skills necessary to navigate an increasingly complex world.

Additionally, addressing systemic barriers such as limited resources and inequitable access to educational opportunities is indispensable for promoting equity and inclusivity at Carol-an National High School. By dismantling these barriers and fostering a more equitable learning environment, educators can ensure that all students have the opportunity to thrive and succeed, regardless of their background or circumstances.

In sum, Hess's report serves as a clarion call for action, compelling educators and stakeholders at Carol-an National High School to redouble their efforts in addressing the pervasive issues of low numeracy and reading skills. By heeding the insights presented in Hess's report and implementing targeted interventions, educators can empower students to unlock their full potential and pursue their goals with confidence, thereby fostering a brighter and more equitable future for all.

Hess's advocacy for data-driven decision-making and continuous improvement aligns closely with the objectives and aspirations of Carol-an National High School. Embracing this approach empowers educators to harness the power of information to drive positive change and enhance student outcomes. By systematically collecting and analyzing data on student performance, educators at Carol-an National High School gain invaluable insights into areas of strength and areas in need of improvement. This data-driven approach enables educators to identify trends, patterns, and areas of need with precision, allowing for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to be implemented where they are most needed. Moreover, by tracking progress over time, educators can monitor the effectiveness of interventions and adjust strategies as necessary, ensuring that students receive the support they need to succeed.

Furthermore, fostering collaboration among teachers, administrators, and community stakeholders is integral to creating a cohesive and supportive learning environment at Carol-an National High School. By promoting open communication and collaboration, educators can share best practices, leverage collective expertise, and pool resources to support student growth and success. This collaborative approach not only enhances the effectiveness of interventions but also fosters a sense of shared responsibility and ownership for student outcomes, ultimately contributing to a more cohesive and enriching educational experience for all stakeholders.

By embracing Hess's emphasis on data-driven decision-making and collaboration, educators at Carol-an National High School can leverage the power of information and collective expertise to drive positive change and enhance student outcomes. Through a commitment to continuous improvement and collaboration, Carol-an National High School can create a supportive and enriching learning environment that nurtures student growth and success, empowering all students to achieve their full potential.

Conclusion

"Still At Risk: What Students Don't Know, Even Now" by Frederick M. Hess emerges as a beacon of guidance amid the challenges of addressing low numeracy and reading skills at Carol-an National High School. Hess's meticulously researched report offers a treasure

trove of insights that, when applied judiciously, can serve as a roadmap for educators and stakeholders grappling with these pressing issues.

By contextualizing Hess's findings within the specific challenges faced by Carol-an National High School, educators and stakeholders gain a nuanced understanding of the root causes and potential solutions to low numeracy and reading skills among students. Hess's report serves as a springboard for targeted interventions tailored to the unique needs and circumstances of the school community. Whether through curriculum adaptations, instructional enhancements, or community partnerships, educators can leverage Hess's recommendations to develop interventions that address the underlying factors contributing to low numeracy and reading skills.

Moreover, Hess's emphasis on collaboration and continuous improvement resonates deeply with the ethos of Carol-an National High School. By fostering a culture of collaboration among educators, administrators, parents, and community stakeholders, the school community can pool its collective wisdom and resources to enact meaningful change. Through collaborative efforts, stakeholders can share best practices, identify emerging trends, and refine interventions in real-time, ensuring that efforts to address low numeracy and reading skills remain responsive and effective.

Ultimately, by embracing the insights and recommendations presented in Hess's report, Carol-an National High School can chart a course toward educational equity and excellence. Through collaborative efforts and a steadfast commitment to continuous improvement, the school community can empower all students to unlock their full potential and thrive in an increasingly complex and interconnected world. With Hess's report as a guiding light, Carol-an National High School can embark on a transformative journey toward a future where every student has the opportunity to succeed and flourish.

Hess's report serves as a beacon of guidance for addressing low numeracy and reading skills at Carol-an National High School. By contextualizing Hess's findings within the specific challenges faced by the school, educators and stakeholders can develop targeted interventions and foster collaboration to enhance student outcomes and promote educational equity. Through a commitment to continuous improvement and collaboration, Carol-an National High School can empower all students to achieve their full potential and thrive academically.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Nick C. Gador, LPT, MED

- Silliman University – Philippines
- Carol-An National High School
Department of Education – Philippines